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Remarking An Analisation

A Study on Maternal Health Scheme and its Implications in Tea Garden Areas with Special Reference to Kellydin and Udmari Tea Garden of Nagaon District of Assam

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Abstract

Assam is the most tea producing state of India and often regarded as the "Tea Gardens of India". So, the tea estate workers hold a significant position in Assam. There are about 11 tea gardens in Nagaon district including tea gardens like Nonoi , Salonah, Amlokhi , Udmari, Kellydin etc. From various previous studies conducted on tea garden workers it was found that the tea garden workers are facing some genuine problems like health and hygiene problem, wage problems etc. These studies also revealed that the women workers of tea garden are facing problems regarding maternal health including wage compensation during pregnancy. In the tea garden of Udmari and Kellyden too women workers are facing same problem. To mitigate this issue, Assam government has adopted some schemes regarding maternal health and tried to implement too. Through these schemes financial assistance is provided to women of the tea estate to support their health and wellbeing during pregnancy and after delivery too. The aim of the scheme is to ensure that the pregnant women can prioritise their health without compromising their families' livelihood and was implemented under State Health Budget. In this study the investigator intends to study the availability of maternal health schemes and its implications among the women of Kellyden and Udmari Tea Garden of Nagaon District.

Keywords Maternal Health, Maternal Health Schemes, Implication.

Introduction

Assam is noteworthy for its tea production. Assam alone contributes more than half of the total production of tea in India and therefore it is often regarded as the "Tea Gardens of India." So, the tea estate workers hold a significant position in Assam. There are about 2500 tea gardens in Assam. Among the tea producing districts of Assam, Nagaon district is one of them. There are about 11 tea gardens in Nagaon district of Assam. Some of the notable tea estates of Nagaon district are Kondoli Tea Estate, Koliabor Tea Estate, Amlokhi Tea Estate, Nonoi Tea Estate, Salona Tea Estate. Later on Jiajuri Tea Estate and Maa Mira Tea Plantation are also included in the list of tea estates of Nagaon district.

Objective of study

1. To study the present scenario of women worker in tea gardens.
2. To study the awareness of women tea workers regarding Maternal Health Scheme.
3. To see the implementation of Maternal Health Scheme in Tea garden areas.

Review of Literature

Rehena , P. (2008) made a study on Health and Economic conditions of tea garden female workers: a study on legal Rights.

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Chetia, Rijumoni . (2014) made a study on Maternal Health Status of Tea garden women in Assam. In her study she discussed in details about the factors related to the less implementation of Maternal Health scheme.

Sharma, M.K. (2017) made a study on Socio-€conomic status of the tea garden women workers with special reference to Bokakhat Sub division of Golaghat district of Assam.

Borgohain , J. (2020) made a study on Tea Garden Women Issues and Socio-Economic Status : A study on Tea Garden Women of Sivasagar District, Assam.

Biswas etal. (2020) made a study on “Exploring the perceptions, practices and challenges to maternal and newborn health care among the underprivileged tea garden community in Bangaladesh : A qualitative study. This study reveals that health facilities ion tea garden is not well equipped to provide good care. Inequities exist within the tea garden communities, with unregistered workers having even poorer access to care. Bhattejee , S. etal. (2013) conducted a study on “Maternal Health care Services Utilization in Tea gardens of Darjeeling, India” . The result of the study revealed low utilization of pregnancy related health care utilization among the study population, especially in case of antenatal care.

Main Text

In tea gardens women play a dominant and important role because in the tea garden workers women are equal bread winners along with their male counterparts. Women workers of tea garden manage both household responsibilities as well as their work in tea estates from early morning to evening yet they get limited recognition in their community. In the tea estates of Nagaon too women workers received limited recognition and they are facing some acquit problems like less wage , maternal health facility, less number of maternity leave in comparison to government employee. In Nagaon district of Assam, the wage Compensation scheme for pregnant women of tea garden areas is a major maternal health initiative. The scheme of wage compensation provides financial assistance to the pregnant women of tea garden areas to support their health and well being during pregnancy and after delivery.

Types of Maternal Health schemes available in tea garden areas:

1. **Wage Compensation Schemes:** This scheme provides financial support to pregnant women of tea garden workers and their family. It enables them to access better health and nutritional facilities. All pregnant women residing in Tea garden areas are eligible for the scheme.
2. **Janani Suraksha Yojana :** This scheme work under National Health Mission . The aim of the scheme is to reduce maternal and infant mortality by promoting institutional deliveries.
3. **Janani Sishu suraksha karyakram :** This scheme provides free and case less delivery services to all pregnant women and sick newborn up to one year of age .
4. **Tea Garden Mobile Medical Units Scheme:** This scheme is launched to provide comprehensive primary health care services. The services of the scheme include maternal health care, child health family planning to tea garden communities.
5. **PPP with Tea Garden Hospitals:** The aim of launching the scheme is to improve healthcare access for tea garden workers and their families. National Health Mission, Assam provides financial help to tea garden hospitals. This service facilitates service delivery including renovation of infrastructure and to purchase necessary equipments for the tea garden hospitals.
6. **Pradhan Mantri Matru Vandana Yajana (women and child development) :** Under this scheme maternity benefit is to be provided to a women for the first two living children provided the second child is a girl.

Present Scenario of Tea Garden Women worker in Assam:

The present scenario of working women in tea garden area especially in Assam reveals a challenging situation. They are contributing equally in tea production workforce yet they often face low wages, having poor economic conditions, and limited access to education and in regards to health care too. In simple words it

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can be said that despite their crucial role, they do not get proper recognition in family, society as well as in their work place too. So, the position of women workers in tea garden areas is not sound in Assam. The present scenario of working women of tea garden areas can be stated as—

1. Low wages and Economic dependence.
2. Poor living condition
3. Poor working conditions.
4. Limited access to education.
5. Gender discrimination.
6. Social issues.
7. Job insecurity.
8. Lack of recognition, etc.

Methodology

Method of Study: Survey method is used for the study.

Sample: The sample of the study consists of 100 women of tea garden areas.

Tools Used Self devised questionnaire

Statistics Used in the Study Kellydin and Udmari Tea Garden.

Result and Discussion

For the study data is collected from the sample with the help of Survey method. The investigator prepared a self devised questionnaire consisting of 30 questions to test their physical health, family condition, economic condition as well as their awareness about the schemes available for them. The questionnaire was set in such a way that they can easily understand by the sample of the study. The questionnaire was given individually and was asked to answer. The investigator helps those samples who are not literate or not able to record the responses in the questionnaire. The investigator also arranges the interview schedule in groups to know directly the tea garden women's feelings and their experiences during pregnancy and after delivery. From the interview schedule it was revealed that the women get only six months maternal leave with six months wage compensation under maternal health schemes. So, they are not happy with the decision of tea garden management authority. They opined that like government employee they too wanted more maternal leave with compensation.

From the study it is observed that most of the women in tea garden areas are not aware of the government schemes available for them. The ASHA karmi of that area make them aware about the schemes of maternal health and its facilities. The reason behind their unawareness about the schemes may be due to lack of education and consciousness. Another reason is due to strict discipline in work place and work load. It is also observed during the interview time they hesitate to disclose the women related issues, which in turn hamper their hygiene. Besides, they have to take the responsibilities of their household work as well as their work in garden from early morning till evening.

Factors like apathy of the tea garden authority towards the government health schemes and the lack of coordination between state government and Tea management authority in implementing the scheme make the women worker helpless. Another factor responsible for poor implementation of maternal Health Scheme is that the government health officials made stressed on the women worker of tea garden area to visit PHC to avail the facilities provided by such schemes.

Conclusion

After analysing the result of the study it can be concluded that women belonging to the tea garden area specially the women tea worker are not aware of the various health rights and available maternal health related schemes and this is because of lack of their awareness. So, to make them aware there is necessity to make them literate first as most of the women in tea garden area are not yet able to get primary education. They are not self motivated to know about such schemes which will support during their pregnancy period. In this regard the ASHA karmi played an important role in making the women aware about those schemes. So, to make the full use of maternal Health scheme, there is need of women education to make them aware of such schemes. Besides there is need to strengthen health care infrastructure, promoting community participation,

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Remarking An Analisation

improving quality of care enhancing accessibility to improve health and wellbeing of the women in tea garden areas.

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